

JOIN US AT THE 9th PROTEONET MEETING

OMICS INTEGRATION

5th April 2019 - h. 14.00

Università degli Studi di Milano - UNITECH OMICs
Viale Ortles 22/4, 20139 Milano (Italy)

GUEST SPEAKER

Henning Hermjakob
Head of Molecular Systems at EMBL-EBI

ORGANIZERS

UNITECH OMICs
Università degli Studi di Milano
Milano, Italy

Angela BACHI
IFOM, Milano, Italy

Tiziana BONALDI
IEO, Milano, Italy

CALL FOR ABSTRACTS

Five short communications will be selected
from contributed abstracts.

Please send your proposal to
proteonet@ifom.eu

no later than 15th March 2019

Purpose of this informal meeting is to foster
interactions and collaborations between
researchers within the proteomics
community in the Milan area and beyond.
The Network is open for all those interested.

Please confirm your participation before
22th March 2019: proteonet@ifom.eu

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piattaforme tecnologiche di ateneo

IEO

European Institute of Oncology

Società Chimica Italiana

Divisione di Spettrometria
di Massa

Italian Proteomics Association